

Paper 6

A Study on The Factors Which Influence the Employee Layoff During Covid-19

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Abstract

The current study understands the factors, which influence the company's and the employee's situations, also to understand the opportunities and challenges for the companies. Any individual employed for wages and salary is known as employee. COVID-19 effected the entire world and the business sectors. Therefore, companies and employees are the once who are directly affected by this pandemic. Because of the drop in the production and sales activities employers are finding it difficult to fund their employees. Hence, they are laying off their employees. Also, some daily wagers lost their job because of the lockdown. "To win in the marketplace you must first win in the workplace (Doug Conant, CEO of Campbell's Soup)."

Term "Employee" is derived from the French word "employee". The concept of working for wages goes back to several years, where people used to work for their livelihood, and it is still in practice. India is a country where the unemployment rate is 5.33% in 2018–19. However, due to the current COVID-19 pandemic the unemployment rate is increased to 5.4% in 2019–20. The call of national wide lockdown was concerned to save the lives of the people in the country, but it had the negative impact on the people who were working for their livelihood.

Entire world trade business stopped their operations, from multinational companies to local "kirana" stores been shut down, which affected the business and slowly it affected the lives of employees who were working in the companies. Companies failed to fulfill the necessities of their employees. Governments failed to make supplementary plans to save the interest of the employees and the employers. According to the study conducted in New Delhi the fear and anxiety level are increasing among the employees. Fear of losing job and anxiety in not getting long awaited appraisals increased the mental stress of the employees.

Employee layoff means temporary or permanent suspension of employment of an employee. The laid off employees are the employees who have lost their jobs because of their employer has closed or moved the company or there was insufficient work. Due to lock down, the entire world-wide market and production center companies' business had seen a down word fall of their share price and market position. Due to lay off, employers are finding it difficult to serve the interest of employees and even found it difficult to pay their salaries. Employee adjustment to the current scenario, this COVID era can be called a completely a disaster and a challenging era. It changed the way of living of people in the world. Uncommon things are turned to be common.

Objectives

- To understand the factors influencing employee layoff.
- To study the condition of employees and the company during the uncertain times.
- To determine the opportunities available for the company's post-pandemic period.
- To analyze the challenges faced by companies and employees during uncertain times.

Key Words: Salaried employees, Daily wage workers, lay off, downsizing, COVID-19 etc.

Introduction to Employee Layoff

Originally the term layoff is used to temporary interruption in work. However, later with passing period it was applied as a permanent suspension of work. Later, these words were used to formally represent as polite way of removing people from their job. Other words that give the same meaning as permanent layoff are downsizing, excess reduction, right sizing etc., it is a strategic plan laid by the company to eliminate many employees or workforce to enhance organizational effectiveness. Lay off has some immediate advantages such as increasing profits, avoiding bankruptcy, redistributing of workforce, but at the same there are few disadvantages, such as reduced skilled workers, and will create stress and pressure on the employees. In short, it reduces the existing employees' satisfaction and commitments toward the organization.

Layoff decisions not necessarily caused by any specific reason, but are outcome of decreasing sales, customers, or resources. Some other reasons for lay off are consequences of mismanagement, fault administration and mergers. Cutting of cost is one of the common reasons used for laying off employees in the organization. Employee layoffs are designed to improve productivity, overall competition, economic outlook, and these, which are used as methods to save companies market position. The following are few companies who announced their downsizing due to COVID-19.

Scandinavian Airlines (SAS) announced that it would temporarily lay off 10,000 employees that is 90% of its staff on March 15.

Norwegian Airlines announced the temporary layoff of 90% of its workforce on March 16, amounting to 7,300 employees.

Marriott International, the world's largest hotel company, said it has started to furlough what could amount to tens of thousands of employees on March 17.

Pebble brook Hotel Trust, which owns over 50 hotels in the US including the W in Los Angeles, laid off 50% of its 8,000 employees on March 17.

New York's Metropolitan Opera on March 19, the Met laid off all of its union employees for the duration of the coronavirus outbreak.

Famous restaurateur Danny Meyer's Union Square Hospitality Group, which owns beloved NYC staples like Gramercy Tavern, laid off 2,000 employees, or 80% of its workforce, on March 18.

Cirque du Soleil announced it is laying off 95% of its 4,679-person staff on March 19, a week after cancelling all its upcoming performances.

Companies' conditions during uncertain times:

Organizational layoffs are designed to improve productivity, economic outlook, and overall competitiveness, and they are perceived as the only way to save companies from bankruptcy. Entire world was completely shut down for the period of more than 2 months. The families that were completely depended upon their business were under loss. The world's great market leaders were not exceptional from the same situation. Majority of the company's shares were valued in negatives. It was not an easy call for companies to lay off their employees who are part of their families. The trusted employees, trained employees, experienced employees were laid off, and had a huge non-monitory loss for the companies, but due to unavoidable reasons, some companies must take out these calls. Some of these reasons are to sustain in business and to retain in the business. In addition, to reduce expenses, entire manufacturing and production sectors were shut down. There were no supplies of raw materials, therefore there was no production, due which no sales and no profit and no returns. Manufactured products were lying in the warehouses. The companies were finding it difficult to run their business. Some difficulties were paying rent for empty office premises, paying internet bills of the employees, providing enough equipment's to do the work from their respective homes, paying salaries, renovation of agreements etc.,

Reasons or factors influencing employee lay off are as follows:

- Economic slowdown
- Increased day to day expenditures
- Mergers and acquisitions:
- Advanced technologies
- Poor management
- False conceptions

Steps in employee layoff:

- **Making the decision:** before issuing any orders, the company management team must sit together and rethink about the decision that they are going to take. They should consider the pros and cons of the decisions, after considering each aspect and taking the consent of all members then the company should finalize the decision.
- **Planning layoff:** after finalizing the decision, you should work on executing the decision, for that proper planning must be done. With the help of heads of the departments and HR you must prepare the list of employees who are going to be laid off. After preparing the list, how to proceed with the decision must be

planned out.

- **Informing the layoff:** once after having the list of employees whom the company is downsizing, a personal meeting must happen. In addition, they must inform the employee regarding management decisions and clear all doubts regarding management decisions.
- **Implementing the action:** after intimating the employees regarding the downsizing, they should work on executing their decision.

Research methodology: It is a contextual framework and a logical scheme based on views, values and beliefs that guides the researchers. Here the secondary data are being used. In addition, the materials referred by websites and e textbooks are used to get the information.

Research question: Research question is a question that the researcher has and works out to find a solution or justification for it. To confirm the objective of the study the following research question was developed. How do the factors influence the employee layoff during COVID-19?

Research Objectives:

- To understand the factors influencing employee layoff.
- To study the condition of employees and the company during the uncertain times.
- To find out the opportunities available for companies the post-pandemic period.
- To analyze the challenges faced by companies and employees during uncertain times.

Factors influencing Employee Layoff:

Several factors influence employee layoffs or downsizing. These are the common reasons or situation for downsizing the employee strength in the organization. The few of them are listed below.

- **The economic slowdown:** due to the pandemic that is faced by the entire business world the economic condition is slow down drastically. This year it was because of the COVID-19 the entire world faced such economic fall. But otherwise, due to various reasons, if there is economic slowdown or recession is faced by the country, the companies to remain in the competition take the step of downsizing.
- **Increased day-to-day expenditures:** these are the problems faced by startup companies or low market power companies. If there are any changes in the day-to-day expenses, they will find it difficult to fund it. It may be due to lack of funds or they might have invested their entire funds in future projects. In such cases, they will adopt the downsizing decision to manage the day-to-day expenses.
- **Mergers and acquisitions:** one of the main reasons for employee layoff is mergers and acquisition. When two companies get merged or financially sound companies acquire small companies, there will be an overflow of the employee

under certain departments. Then, the management will take the call to remove the excess employees from the overloaded departments.

- **Advanced technologies:** some of the experienced staff in the departments are not technically skilled. Due to which they are not good in adapting the changes taking places in the business world. Because of this reason, management finds it difficult to retain such technically unskilled employees.
- **Poor management:** sometimes due to the wrong management decision or poor management by the top-level management teams, they will fail to find solutions for the problem, and sometimes incur losses due to their wrong judgments and it effects the entire business condition. To compensate for losses, they will lay off the employees from the business.
- **Wrong decisions:** sometimes due to the wrong decisions of the management or heads of the department, they miscalculate the situation or the project and invest in the wrong projects. In addition, to come over the losses of their wrong decisions they use employee layoff techniques.

Challenges faced by the companies during COVID-19 are

- **Severe decline in sales:** the major challenge that is faced by the companies worldwide is declining in the sales. It was not due to no demand in the market, but it was due to no timely supplies. As we all know the entire world was completely shut down for the period of more than 2 months, the entire business operations were shut closed. So, no business, no transportation, no production hence there is no sales.
- **The lack of sufficient funds:** there were no funds available to face this pandemic effectively. The companies are not ready to manage such situations, due to the lack of liquid and emergency funds it was difficult for them to manage their employees. In addition, unavoidable expenses such as the payment of rents, electricity bills, internet bills etc. must be paid by the companies.
- **Restricted logistic supports:** as the world was fighting against pandemic due to which other than the necessities nothing was available as and when needed. There were no supplies because the entire world was supporting the country to fight against the coronavirus. Hence, companies could not deliver their finished product to their customers on time.
- **Increase in operational cost:** the lockdown shifted all the work from office to home. Both workplace and house day-to-day expenses are increasing drastically. Such as internet bills, phone bills, rent, EMI's, etc., nobody was responsible for such a situation as it is a sudden outburst. Whatever funds were available; it was used for meeting the necessities. Due to the long lock down and safety measures, regaining the situation was difficult.
- **Maintaining social distancing:** each part of the world finding it difficult to maintain the social distancing. The people are used to work together, be together now it's difficult to change the built habit suddenly. However, this is one of the major requirements to start the operation. Only if the companies can fulfill the

requirement and take necessary actions to prevent social gathering among the employees then only the government is providing permission to start the business.

- **The lack of experienced employees:** due to COVID-19 pandemic, companies were unable to fulfill the demands of the employees. Some companies due to their financial problems without any choice they had to remove many people from the jobs. Some due to traveling issues and COVID-19 fear of getting infected by the virus left the organization. Because of this, companies lost their experienced employees and found it difficult to train new employees.

Layoffs decisions may not be because of any specific fault of the employees but can be a consequence of decreasing sales or customers, cash, material resources within the organization.

Opportunities for companies during the pandemic situation are

Opportunity is a time or set of circumstances or situations that makes it possible to do something or to achieve something. As there is a saying “nothing is more expensive than a missed opportunity”. If you miss your opportunities, you miss out your chance to be outstanding. Even this great pandemic has given several opportunities to grab the situation and to use it for benefits. Some of these opportunities were as follows:

- **The entry of new talents:** due to pandemic majority of the companies in the world lost their experience and skilled employees. Simultaneously, this pandemic has given the chance to use fresh talents. When you get a raw talent, you can use as much as you want. They will be technically skilled and will have the interest to learn new things. In addition, there is a bold and challenging young generation. The companies can use their skills for further development.
- **Crisis created new needs:** due to this great crisis many needs and demands created in the market. People are looking forward to using the local product and support the country. In addition, they discovered a way of buying and using the local products. In addition, know the importance of economic development.
- **Changes in the approach:** there is a drastic change in the world business markets. Before the breakdown of the pandemic, people used to buy the product manufactured in other countries, which had adverse impact on the Country's GDP. But post-pandemic people are giving importance and preferring domestic products over foreign products. In addition, contributing to the country's economy.
- **Government support:** As you all know, government has undertaken lot measures to prevent spreading of COVID-19, but at the same time they were concerned about the Indian economy. In addition, the people of the country. So, they came with different protects. Such as ‘VOCAL FOR LOCAL’, and less interest loan, and concession in tax payment etc., because of these support people of the country are much interested in doing business and starting up their own.
- **Usage of user-friendly technologies:** though the technology was built up way

long back, still the people are not adapting to it. However, after the pandemic where the physical exchange of any product is dangerous to our own health, made the people to use technology, and go digital. Now for the payment of cash and purchasing goods, materials, anything people prefer online platform.

Conclusion:

COVID-19 is a worst case that happened to the entire world. Though we faced the outburst of diseases, it is still unpredictable. We cannot highlight at one thing and say that is the only thing that has affected by the pandemic, but every sector is been affected, for example, travel industry, day to workers, constructors, roadside sellers, people staying in rented house, running small business. Schools and colleges, aviation industry, each sector has been affected. It has a great impact on the negative move of GDP of the country.

The biggest problem that affected the entire world is an increase in the rate of unemployment. This pandemic has added the points to the existing unemployment. New hiring was freeze for a long period as the entire business market was down. Adding to it the companies are forced their employees to leave the job. Because of no other reason to survive in the business, sales were down, no production, no income flow, but there was an outflow of money such as rent payment for the empty premises and warehouses, electricity payments, internet bills, telephone bills, tax payments etc.,

The study was conducted to understand the various factors that influence the employee layoff in the corporate sectors. From the study it was clear that every business sector had been affected by this pandemic. In addition, the situation made the employers to remove the people from the job. However, due to the timely support of the government of the country, people could face this pandemic and now because of the different projects of the government people are starting up their own business and working on it. Few people started to follow their long-lasting dreams, and few were pursuing higher education, which was incomplete, and still few more people are enhancing their talents using digital platform.

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